

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17695229

Analysis Of The Effects Of Banditry And Kidnapping In Southern Kaduna, Kaduna State, Nigeria

Sarka S.W¹ & Magaji J. Y.²

¹Department of Public Administration, National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria

²Department of Geography and Environmental Management, University of Abuja, Nigeria.

Corresponding Author's E-Mail: sswogan@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

This study analyses the effects of banditry and kidnapping on socio-economic activities of the residents of Southern Kaduna. The study adopted a cross sectional survey, and used stratified sampling techniques in selecting the respondents. A sample size of 382 respondents was obtained using Krejcie & Morgan, (1970) model for sample selection. Information on the demographic characteristics of the respondents, incidences, causes, effects and mitigation of banditry and kidnapping were collected using news papers, television, radio, internet and questionnaire. The data collected were summarized using simple percentage and frequency distribution table. Results show that majority of the residents dependent on agriculture. It revealed that there are incessant clashes, killings, banditry and kidnappings in the area. Findings shows that the major causes of the clashes, banditry and kidnappings are Farmers/Fulani herdsmen clashes (53%), cows grazing on peoples farms (7%); banditry exists as a result of Jihad (18%). Among the effects of banditry and kidnapping includes destruction of lives and properties (99.5%), increase in poverty of local residents, Shortage in agricultural outputs of the farmers (96.6), disruption of social activities e.g. festivals, educational (96.1%), trauma, rendering people as refugees, shutting down of small businesses and social gatherings. In order to avoid being abducted or kidnapped, the following tips are necessary; prayer, avoiding discussing money publicly, alert people's attention whenever you notice a threat and refusing to accept rides from strangers, avoiding public donations among others. It is recommended that there should be sustainable military efforts in prosecuting the banditry by equipping the security forces with modern equipments; there is need for massive employment of youths in the armed forces; and Nigerian government should strategize to create meaningful employment for the youths trapped in the phenomenon through the creation of programmes aim at addressing the endemic poverty in the country.

Keywords: Armed Banditry, Kidnapping, Effects of Banditry and Kidnapping, Socio-Economic Activities, Southern Kaduna, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

The pervasive banditry and its associated threats to security, which have enveloped the Northwest region of Nigeria, particularly, Zamfara, Katsina, Kaduna, Sokoto and Kebbi States, have become a worrisome national security issue of public concern (Olaniyan & Yahaya, 2016).

Reports indicate the flourishing of bandit groups, whose members were seen displaying automatic weapons, terrorizing herders' settlements, farms, villages and the highways with the mission of killing people, kidnapping and pillaging cows (Olaniyan, 2018). It was reported that between October, 2013 and March, 2014, 7,000 cattle were rustled from commercial livestock farms and traditional herders in Northern Nigeria (Bashir, 2014; Tauna, 2016) while about 330 attacks were made by bandits and 1,460 deaths were recorded between January and July, 2019 (Abdullahi, 2019). In most cases, the bandits killed

and maimed the people and raped the women before dispossessing them of their cows (Akowe & Kayode, 2014), while in some instances, they also kidnapped women in the process (Adeniyi, 2015; Yusuf, 2015). Suffice to say that the northwestern region of Nigeria encompasses seven states namely Kano, Jigawa, Katsina, Kaduna, Zamfara, Sokoto and Kebbi. Five of these states, which are Katsina, Kaduna, Zamfara, Sokoto and Kebbi have been mostly affected by the scourge of banditry. Of these five states, Kaduna, Katsina and Zamfara have been the most critical hot spots. It is however, pertinent to note that the incidences of banditry are not limited to northwestern Nigeria. In fact, it is also prevalent in some parts of north-central region, in states like Niger, Nasarawa, Benue and Plateau which are equally regarded as hotbeds (Kuna & Jibrin, 2016).

Scholars like Olaniyan & Yahaya (2016), Suleiman (2017) and Mustapha (2019) have advanced several factors for the cause and prevalence of banditry in Nigeria. Some of the factors they argued include the fragility of Nigerian state, weak state institutions, especially the security agencies, availability of grossly ungoverned spaces, porosity of Nigeria's borders with, arms proliferation, weak leadership, corruption, unemployment and mass poverty. Furthermore, despite the federal framework adopted by Nigeria's forefathers, Nigeria's security architecture since the incursion of the military in Nigeria's politics is contrived in such a manner that the control of every security outfit is placed in the hands of the President at the centre. Though the governor is recognised by Nigeria's constitution as the Chief Security Officer of the state, in actual fact, he wields no power over the police that could be put to use in times of crisis. This precarious situation places every governor at the mercy of the President in the period of crisis at the state level denying them the opportunity to confront security challenges with expediency and expertise. This is one of the reasons why people are clamoring for restructuring that will, among others, effect the creation of state police to meet the immediate needs of every state.

There is no gainsaying the fact that banditry poses a serious challenge not only to the security of Northwest states but to the country at large in view of its ever increasing impacts and implications. The level at which armed bandits operate within the northwest region calls for attention by both the State and Federal governments, more especially, since the latter controls the state security apparatuses. This complex situation of social violence and insecurity in the affected states had been on for almost a decade now (Okoli & Ogayi, 2018). The increasing attacks of bandit groups have led to the destruction of lives and properties, displacement of people from their communities; and a growing numbers of widows; widowers and orphans, who now reside in Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) camps following the continued attacks of armed bandits on both farming and pastoral communities across different areas of the states (Okoli & Ochim, 2016; Mustapha, 2019).

This is a threat to Nigeria's socio-economic development, thus inhibiting the efficient and effective performance of government. Some of the affected communities are located in remote areas where there is little or no government presence. More importantly, households and schools are in some cases separated by interspersed buildings with forest areas, rendering them vulnerable to banditry. This situation is worse by the absence of effective community policing mechanisms capable of addressing the hinterlands' peculiar security challenges which affected government efforts in fighting banditry in the Northwest. It is against this background that the study tends to investigate the incidence, causes and effects of Banditry and kidnappings on the socio economics activities of the people in southern Kaduna.

1.3 Study Objectives

1. To investigate the incidence of armed Banditry and Kidnappings in the study area.
2. To investigate the causes of Armed Banditry and Kidnappings in the area.
3. To identify the effects of Armed Banditry and Kidnappings in the area
4. Examine their Coping Strategies

CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

Concept of Banditry

Banditry is a derivative of the term bandit, meaning an unlawful armed group terrorising people and confiscating their properties. It is synonymous with the establishment of gang groups who use small and light weapons to carry out attacks against people. In this regard, banditry could mean a set-up criminal activity deliberately designed and carried out for personal gains. Due to the complex nature of bandits' activities, Egwu (2016) in a restricted manner, described banditry as a practice of stealing cattle and animals from herders or raiding of cattle from their ranches. In the same vein, banditry is reflected in criminal escapades like cattle rustling, kidnapping, armed robbery, drug abuse, arson, rape and the brazen and gruesome massacre of people of agrarian communities with sophisticated weapons by suspected herdsmen and reprisal attacks from surviving victims, a development that has been brought to the front burner of national security (Uche & Iwuamadi, 2018).

In his perception, Shalangwa (2013) regards banditry as the practice of raiding and attacking victims by members of an armed group, whether or not premeditated, using weapons of offence or defense, especially in semi-organised groups for the purpose of overpowering the victim and obtaining loot or achieving some political goals. Such bandits are usually perceived as outlaws, desperate and lawless marauders who do not have a definite residence or destination but roam around the forest and mountains to avoid being identified, detected and arrested.

Therefore, bandits are gang groups terrorising and dispossessing local people or travelers of their valuable items or properties such as merchandise, money, cattle, camel, and sheep, among others for primitive accumulation of wealth. They operate within and along rural borders with the assistance of their local collaborators including in some cases, state agents deployed to work for the safety and security of the people (Abdullahi, 2019).

Thus banditry, is here by defined as the totality of incidences of armed robbery or allied violent crimes, such as kidnapping, cattle rustling, village raids as well as highway raids which involves the use of force, or threat to that effect, to intimidate a person or a group of persons in order to rob, rape, kidnap or kill the victims.

Concept of Security and Insecurity

The term security has not till date been accorded a universal conceptual outlook due to the fact that it has been considered from different perspectives. Some scholars like Igbuzor (2011) and Oche (2001) while conceptualising security placed emphasis on the absence of threats to peace, stability, national cohesion, political and socio-economic objectives of a country. It is conceived as to be secure and free from both fear of physical, psychological abuse, violence, persecution, or death and from want such as food, health and good job (Asmau & Abdurashed, 2020). Also, Omede (2011) sees security as a dynamic condition which involves the relative ability of a state to counter threats to its core values and interests.

Security can further be described as stability and continuity of livelihood (stable and steady income), predictability of daily life (knowing what to expect), protection from crime (feeling safe), and freedom from psychological harm (safety or protection from emotional stress which results from the assurance or knowing that one is wanted, accepted, loved and protected in one's community or by people around (Nwanegbo & Odigbo, 2013). It also focuses on emotional and psychological sense of belonging to a social group which can offer one protection. This description of the foregoing structured the concept of security into four dimensions. These dimensions can be woven together to give a composite definition of security as the protection against all forms of harm whether physical, economic or psychological (Olabanji & Ese, 2014).

It is, however, contended that security is not the absence of threats or security issues, but the ability to rise to the challenges posed by these threats with expediency and expertise. It demands safety from chronic threats and protection from harmful disruption (Igbuzor, 2011). Security embraces all measures designed to protect and safeguard the citizenry and the resources of individuals, groups, businesses and the nation against sabotage or violent occurrence (Ogunleye, Adewale, Alese, & Ogunde, 2013).

On the other hand, the concept of insecurity connotes different meanings such as: absence of safety; danger; hazard; uncertainty; lack of protection, and lack of safety. Beland (2005) opined that insecurity is the state of fear or anxiety stemming from a concrete or alleged lack of protection. It refers to lack or inadequate freedom from danger. Achumba, Ighomereho & Akpor-Rabaro (2013) define insecurity from two perspectives. Firstly, insecurity is the state of being open or subject to danger or threat of danger, where danger is the condition of being susceptible to harm or injury. Secondly insecurity is the state of being exposed to risk or anxiety, where anxiety is a vague unpleasant emotion that is experienced in anticipation of some misfortune. From the exposition above, the phenomenon of security or insecurity implies both physical occurrence and psychological state of mind that constitutes a challenge to peace and development of both the individuals and the societies. These definitions of either security or insecurity indicate that those affected by insecurity in the Northwest region of Nigeria are many.

Theoretical Framework

This paper adopted Queer Ladder Theory (QLT) and Frustration-Aggression Theory as its analytical frameworks. The origin of Queer Ladder Theory (QLT) is associated with an American sociologist, Daniel Bell (1919-2011), who coined the idea of “queer ladder” in an attempt to explain the instrumental essence of organised crime as a desperate means of socio-economic empowerment and social climbing. This theoretical perspective has since fertilised into a popular theoretical framework widely used in contemporary crime studies. The basic assumptions of QLT are; organised crime is an instrumental behaviour, it is a means to an end; it is an instrument of social climbing and/or socio-economic advancement; and it is a measure to accumulate wealth and build power (Mallory, 2007; Okoli & Orinya, 2013).

Often ascribed to Queer Ladder Theory is the notion that organised crime thrives in contexts where the government’s capacity to dictate, sanction and deter crime is poor; where public corruption is endemic; and where prospects for legitimate livelihood opportunities are slim (Nwoye, 2000; Lyman, 2007). Under these circumstances, the incentive to indulge in crime is high, while deterrence from criminal living is low. In other words, the benefits of committing a crime surpass the costs and/or risks involved. This creates pretext for criminal impunity and franchise (Okoli & Orinya, 2013).

Applied to the context of this study, QLT enables one to come to terms with the prevalence of organised crime in Northwest Nigeria. In this regard, it is observed that the phenomenon of banditry in the region has been driven by criminal quest for economic accumulation in an environment. This has been worsened by the prevailing socio-economic discontent and attendant livelihood crisis in the state, in addition to the seeming indolence of relevant government agencies towards arresting the ugly situation. The concept of ‘Ladder’ in QLT signifies untoward pattern of social mobility. Hence, those who take to organised crime, such as banditry, do so as a desperate means of economic accumulation and socio-economic empowerment (Mustapha, 2019). Therefore, a necessary consequence of this trend is prevalence in crime rate and a state of insecurity (Okoli & Orinya, 2013).

The frustration-aggression theory was propounded by Fererabend & Feirauben, (1972) and captured in a monograph by five scholars in Yale Institute of Human Relations in 1939. The major assumption of the model is that aggression is always a consequence of frustration, and that the occurrence of aggressive behaviour always presupposes the existence of frustration and, contrariwise, that the existence of frustration always leads to some form of aggression (Dollard, Miller, Doob, Mowrer, & Sears, 1939; Fererabend & Feirauben, 1972). They also defined frustration as an interference with the occurrence of an instigated goal response at its proper time in the behaviour sequence (Dollard et al., 1939). The interrogations and disputations that the perspective generated led one of the proponents to intervene with some modifications of the central thesis.

Thus, Miller (1941) noted that it was too general to assume that frustration must always lead to aggression or that aggression is always propelled by frustration. His intervention led to the second lap of the hypothesis which reflected a more acceptable reality that frustration produces instigations to a number of different types of response, one of which is instigation to some form of aggression. However, some

years later, a significant modification came from Berkowitz (1989) who argued that aggression can be driven by inherent personal benefits to the aggressor and not necessarily by past wrongdoings and that people are more akin to attack when they discover that they are willfully sabotaged or denied what it's legitimately theirs than when the interference is an accidental occurrence. He surmised that frustrations are aversive events and generate aggressive inclinations only to the extent that they produce negative effect.

Thus, the increasing attacks of bandits across the country, most especially in the northwest region, are largely driven by frustrations and struggles to generate economic assets. The alarming acts of banditry such as cattle rustling, kidnapping, physical attacks and encroachments on farms are bred by frustrations (Uche & Iwuamadi, 2018). Furthermore, Fererabend & Feirauben (1972) stipulates that aggression is as a result of frustration which results from an individual's inability to attain their goals. Accordingly, banditry is the product of aggressive behaviour which results from issues such as poverty and unemployment, among others (Maureen & Blessing, 2018; Adegoke, 2019). Applying this to the study, banditry in the country is caused by the need of the disgruntled elements of the society to get out of poverty and climb up the ladder in socio-economic considerations. That is why the phenomenon of ransom taking is prevalent in banditry operations. However, where the ransom is not forthcoming, bandits became more tensed and frustrated and resort to killing their victims. This is why the two theories become mutually reinforcing and complementary in explaining the crisis at hand.

METHODOLOGY

The Study Area is Southern Kaduna (formerly Southern Zaria), it is an area inhabited by various non-Hausa peoples living south of Zaria Emirate of Kaduna State. It is located in the Middle Belt region of Nigeria. Southern Kaduna consists of 12 local Government out of 23 Local Governments in Kaduna State, namely: Chikun, Jaba, Jema'a, Kachia, Kaduna South, Kagarko, Kajuru, Kaura, Kauru, Lere, Sanga, and Zangon Kataf.

Figure 1: Map of Kaduna showing Southern Kaduna

Southern Kaduna is composed of closely related ethnic groups and several subgroups united by a common culture and history, classified based on their ethno-linguistic affinities (James, 2000). Southern Kaduna population is estimated to be over 4.5 million people out of the estimated 8.5 million population in Kaduna state in 2016.

The study employed cross-sectional research design whereby data were collected at one point in time using a structured questionnaire for individual respondents and checklists for key informants. Furthermore, the design was considered to be suitable for determining relationships between and among variables (Kothari, 2009).

The data used for this study comprises of both Primary and Secondary sources. The Primary sources include the personal observation during reconnaissance and field survey using a structured questionnaire with multiple choices with little interview granted to some few people. The secondary data source includes published and unpublished materials, journal articles, text books, paper presentation, internet, lecture notes, government reports, gazettes and unpublished thesis that relates to the study.

The researchers conducted a reconnaissance survey in November, 2021, in order to identify the communities that were mostly affected and the population characteristics that make up the study area. They went round the settlements in order to get familiarized with the terrain of the environment and to decide the sampling techniques to be employed. Observations were also made on few things on the field.

The population of the study area comprises of all the residence of Zangon Kataf Local government and its environment. The population of the selected settlements were been estimated by the village heads. A total of 58,771 households were identified and listed during the reconnaissance.

Using the population of 58,771 households obtained in the field from the selected settlements, a sample population, 382 was obtained. The study area was stratified into five areas, namely: Chukun, Zango Kataf, Kagoro, Kafanchan, Kachia, Kagarko and Sanga. The sample size was determined by adopting the Krejcie & Morgan (1970) formula for determining for sample size of a giving population thus:

$$S = \frac{X^2 NP(1-P)}{d^2 (N-1) + X^2 P(1-P)}$$

Where:

S= required sample size.

X²=the table value of chi-square for 1 degree of freedom at the desired confidence level (3.841).

N = the population size.

P = the population proportion (assumed to be 0.50 since this would provide the maximum sample size).

D = the degree of accuracy expressed as a proportion (.05).

The sampled size proportional to the population of the Local governments is 58,771.

Table 3.1 Sample Frame

Settlement	Population of the Household	Sampled household
Chukun	4667	30.3
ZangoKataf	7798	50.7
Kagoro	8864	57.7
Kafanchan	9787	63.6
Kachia	9508	61.8
Kagarko	9357	60.8
Sanga	8790	57.1
Total	58771	382

Source: Field survey, 2022

The questionnaire was analyzed using descriptive statistics with the aid of the Microsoft Excel and Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), and the results was presented in simple percentage tables.

RESULTS PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Gender

Table 4.1 Sex Distribution of the Respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	213	55.8
Female	169	44.2
Total	382	100

Source: Field work, 2022.

Table 4.1 revealed that 55.8% representing 382 of the respondents were males, while 44.2% were females. The dominance of males in the survey is not surprising considering the fact that men are basically breadwinners in their respective homes/families and only supported by their wives or spouses. Also, in this part of the world, men are given more preference to women in land ownership issues which could be responsible for the high number. Similar male dominance was reported by Obinna, Owei and Okwakpam, (2010) in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The result obtained is however at variance with the findings of Abduselam and Belay, (2018) in Addis Ababa where women dominated the survey. The difference could be attributed to location of the study and cultural differences.

Age of the Respondents

Table 4.2: Age Distribution of the Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
(25-30)yrs	24	6.3
(31-35)yrs	50	13.2
(36-40)yrs	103	28.5
(41-45)yrs	98	25.7
(46-50)yrs	35	9.2
(51yrs & above)	64	16.6
Total	382	100

Source: Field work, 2022

The age distribution of the respondents is presented in Table 4.2, the result shows that 7.3% representing 24 respondents is between (25-30)yrs, 13.1% representing 50 respondents is between (31-35)yrs, 27%, 25.7% 9.2% and 16.8% of the respondents representing 103, 98, 35, and 64 respondents are between the ages of 36-40, 41-45, 46-50, and 51years and above respectively. This analysis shows that about 52.7% of the respondents are between the ages of (36-45) yrs, which also fall within the active age. This was also, observed by Obinna *et al.*, (2010) that people of aged (20-44 yrs) dominated his respondents. This means that young adults (active population) dominate the area and are involved in different occupation to make ends meet. Similar age pattern was reported Abduselam and Belay, (2018) where respondents aged (35-45) yrs dominated the study of perceived effects of development induced displacement. However, the implication of the age distribution is that since majority of the respondents are adults it implies that reliable information can be obtained from them.

Marital Status

Table 4.3 Distribution of the Respondents by Marital Status

Marital status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	114	29.8
Married	244	63.9
Divorced	11	2.9
Widow/widower	13	3.4

Source: Field work, 2022

The marital status of respondents showed that 29.8% of them are single, 63.9% are married, while 2.9% and 3.4% are divorced and widow/widower respectively. This information therefore shows that a greater percentage of the respondents in the area who are affected by the urbanization process are married and have families. This result suggests that married individuals dominated the survey.

Family Size

Table 4.4 Distribution of the Respondents by Family Size

Family size	Frequency	Percentage
2 persons	21	5.5
(3-5) persons	46	12
(6-9) persons	58	15.2
10 persons& above	142	37.2

Source: Field work, 2022

Table 4.4 reveals that 37.2% representing 142 respondents have a household size of between 10 persons and above, followed by 58 respondents representing 15.2% who have between (6-9) persons, 46 respondents representing 12% have (3-5) persons in a household, while 21 respondents representing 5.5% of the households has 2 persons. This suggests that majority of the households in the area have 6 and above persons that were usually wipe out or displaced due to absence of shelter.

Educational Level

Table 4.5: Distribution of the Respondents by Educational Level

Educational attainment	Frequency	Percentage
No formal education	23	6.0
Primary	50	13.1
Secondary	172	45.0
Tertiary	137	35.9
Total	382	100

Source: Field work, 2022

The distribution of educational attainment of the respondents is presented in Table 4.5. The results showed that 45.0% of the respondents had Secondary Education and 35.9% had Tertiary Education while 13.1% and 6.0% had primary education and no formal education respectively. The result simply indicates that 80.9% of the respondents have secondary and tertiary education, indicating that the respondents are literate, which will help in supplying vital information on the topic of study.

Occupational status

The occupational status of the respondents is presented in Table 4.

Table 4.6: Distribution of the Respondents by Occupational Status.

Occupational status	Frequency	Percentage
Farming	50	13
Civil servant	101	26.4
Trading	141	36.9
Artisan	75	19.6
Total	382	100

Source: Field work, 2022

The results show that 36.9% representing 141 respondents are traders of various categories. 26.4% of the respondents are civil servants; while 19.6% were engaged artisans for their livelihood. This implies that the respondents are involved in different occupations as their means of livelihood.

The result obtained further suggests that the workforce in the area of study is dominated by traders, civil servants, and farmers. These occupations no doubt can be seriously impacted by urbanization if the process of development is not well planned. The displacement of people for instance could undermine their occupation thereby negatively impacting on household income and source of sustenance.

Income Level

Table 4.7: Distribution of the Respondents by Income Level

Income	Frequency	Percentage
Below ₦18,000	29	7.6
₦18,000-₦30,000	84	22
₦31,000-₦40,000	132	34.6
₦41,000 & above	137	35.9
Total	382	100

Source: Field work, 2022

Table 4.7 presents the results of the monthly income of the respondents. The average monthly income of respondents showed that 35.9% representing 137 respondents earned ₦41,000 and above, 34.6% of the respondents earned ₦31,000-₦40,000 monthly; 22% earned ₦18,000 - ₦30,000 monthly; 3.9% earned below ₦18,000 per month. This means that majority (70.4%) of the people surveyed earned ₦31,000 and above per month, which depends on the nature of job they engage into in the area. The study further indicates that the respondents are low-income individuals who can be impacted greatly by the aftermath of urbanization such as relocation or displacement without proper support from the government.

Incidences of Banditry and Kidnappings in Kaduna State

Table 4.8: Incidences of Banditry and Kidnappings in Kaduna state

S/No	Source	Reporter(s)	Date Posted	Events and outcome
1	The cable news	The cable		A total of 274 persons kidnapped along Abuja-Kaduna highway which accounted for the most people kidnapped in Kachia and Kagarko LGAs
2	Dailytrust.com	Inside story		29 people killed by suspected herdsmen rendering 1000 people homeless in Godo-Godo in Jama'a LGA.
3	Vanguard	Luka Baniyat		Fulani/Atakar war; over 10,000 Atakar were displaced due to the violence.
4	Justrecent.wordpress.com	News	13/12/2012	19 people killed; four villages sacked over the death of 2 cows
5	businessstandard.com	News	05/02/2014	24 people killed; 14 from Dajet and 6 from Atakar
6	Allafrica.com	Emmanuel Adam; LGA C/man	24/06/2014	28 people killed in Sangan
7	This day News	John Shiklan	16/03/2019	Bandits attacked and killed 10 persons, injured 2 and 30 houses torched in Nandu village Sanga
8	Punch.ng.com	News	16/03/2019	Bandits attacked and killed 2 persons in NanduGbok village Sanga LGA.
9	Nigerian Tribune	MuhammedSabiu	02/03/2020	Bandits killed 50 people and several others injured some villages in Igabi and Giwa LGA of Kaduna State
10	Vanguard.ng.com		14/02/ 20	1 person killed and 5 others injured in MaroKachia.
11	Nijanews	BusayoOkunloye	16/03/2020	10 persons killed, 30 houses burnt in Sanga LGA
12	Saharareporter	Sahara reporter	31/03/20 22	2 persons killed in AnkwaKachia.

13	The Vanguard	Ibrahim Hassan Wugo	04/02/20 22	11 persons killed and many injured Kagoro.
14	The Nation	AbdulGafarAlabelew e	24/04/2020	Bandits killed seven and kidnapped one in Akwunakwo, Kabirasha and Damba villages in Chikun LGA of Kaduna State.
15	Vanguard	Vanguard	05/12/2020	Bandits attack KasuwanMagani town in Kajuru LGA of Kaduna State, where 1 person was killed
16	The cable news	The cable	20/07/2020	16 persons were killed in an attack during wedding celebration in kukumdaji, kaura LG
17	The Nation	Abdul GafarAlabelewe	26/7/2020	Bandits killed 10 people in two attacks in 3 villages of Jema'a and Kaura LGA of Kaduna State.
18	Nijanews	BusayoOkunloye	9/03/2020	About 100 persons killed, and over 100 people were rendered homeless in Kajuru LGA
19	The Punch	OlaideOyelude	09/08/2020	Eight bandits attacked and killed 2 persons in Zamfarawa village Batsari LGA of Kastina State
20	Vanguard	Ibrahim HassanWugo	13/09/2020	Bandits abducted 16 family members at Udawa farming community of Kaduna State
21	Vanguard	Ibrahim Hassan Wu go	17/11/2020	Bandits kidnap 8 ABU students on the Kaduna-Abuja road and also killed a district head of GidanZaki, ZangonKataf LGA and his son.
22	Sahara reporter		18/11/2020	Nine ABU students abducted along Kaduna-Abuja road and demanded a ransom of 270m.
23	Sahara reporter		24/11/2020	I person killed, while two shot with serious injury in Meginginya, Igabi LGA
24	The cable news	The cable	12/09/2020	17 persons were kidnapped on their way to farm in KukumDaji, Kaura LG
25	The cable news	The cable	15/03/2021	In igabilg, 152 persons, killed, 411 kidnapped and 1536 head of cattle rustled.
26	Vanguard.ng.com		24/06/ 21	12 persons were abducted in Kachia.
27	Arise news		25/06/ 21	Four children were kidnapped and one persons was killed while others were beaten in Kachia.
28	NAN	News	26/06/2021	Police confirms Bandit attacked of unspecified number of travelers along Kaduna-Kachia road.
29	Daily Trust	Ahmed Ali	27/09/2021	30 people were killed and many houses raze in Madmai and Abun village in Kaura LGA
30	Daily trust	Mohammed I. Yaba	01-02-2022	Bandits killed over 1192 people and abducted 3348 across the Kaduna state in 2021.
31	Daily trust	Mohammed I. Yaba	01-02-2022	Bandits killed a total of 343 people and 830 abducted between July and September 2021in Kaduna state in 2021.
32	Vanguard	Ibrahim H. Wuyo	30/01/2022	10 people were killed in Mawai community ZamanDabo village

33	The cable news	KunleDaramola	16/02/2022	ZangoKataf Chiefdom. 22 people were kidnapped, 4 people injured in Idon town Kajuru.
34	Channelstv.com		17/03/22	More than 63 people abducted by suspected bandits in AgunuDutse and Katul communities in Kachia.
35	Niyitabity.net		20/03/2022	34 people were killed by gunmen on Sunday in Kagoro
36	Channelstv.com	ChimezieEnyiocha	21/03/2022	34 persons killed in Kaura LG., over 200 houses and 32 shops were burnt, the vehicles and 17 motorcycles were vandalized by armed gang
37	Vanguard	Ibrahim Hassan-Wuyo	22-03-2022	bandits have killed no fewer than 43 persons in Southern Kaduna,
38	Daily post	John Gabriel	22/03/2022	Two soldiers and 32 residents were killed. Over 200houses were and 32 shops were burnt. Three vehicles and 17 motorcycles were vandalized
39	Vanguard	Ibrahim H. Wuyo	23/03/2022	Bandits attacked Fountain Baptist Church and shattered their window glasses.
40	The Punch	Geofrey Gorge	26/03/2022	On 20 th March, 20211, in AgbanKagoro, 38 people were killed and several houses burnt.
41		Solomon Elusojj	28/03/2022	Kaduna train attack victims die from gunshot injuries.
42	The Guardian	SaxoneAkaine I	17/04/2022	In AgbanKagoro, two people were killed and several others were injured.
43	The cable news	The cable	05/04/2022	11 soldiers killed by gunmen in military base Kaduna

Source: Field survey, 2022

Table 4.8 presents the incidences of armed banditry and Kidnappings in Kaduna. A close observation shows that kidnappings and banditry were carried out on regular bases. Once the strike in one village, they will change to another direction. Formally they used to take people by surprise, but now they notify the settlements before their operations. People now live in fear and can never discharge their duties regularly. This causes a lot of loss of lives, destruction of properties, traumatizing the victims among others.

Causes of Banditry and Kidnappings in Kaduna State

Table 4.9: Causes of Banditry and Kidnapping

Causes of banditry and kidnappings	Frequency	Percent
Farmers/Fulani herdsmen clashes	203	53
Region jihad	58	18
Cows grazing on peoples farms	27	7
Hausas wanting to dominate the natives	19	5
Political influence,	27	7
Joblessness ,	23	6
Terrorism,	15	4
Total	382	100

Source: Field Survey, 2022

When the respondents were asked for the causes of banditry and kidnapping in their areas, their answers is presented in Table 4.9. The major causes of the clashes are Farmers/Fulani herdsmen clashes which were indicated by 53% representing 203 respondents. This started when two cows were discovered death and was suspected to be poisoned. The Fulanis then launched attack and killed several people, burnt their

houses and rendered them homeless. Another cause for the Farmers/Fulani clashed was a situation where the herdsmen push their cows to graze on peoples farms and destroyed all their crops.

On the issue of banditry, 18% of the respondents were with the opinion that banditry exists as a result of Jihad. That people are been terrorized, demoralized, humiliated in order to be conquered and convert to Islam. That the Fulanis claim that their farther is on the throne and Nigeria is their inheritance.

Other reasons include: lack of capital punishment by the government, Hausas wanting to dominate the natives, political influence, joblessness, terrorism among others.

Effects of Banditry and Kidnappings on the Socioeconomic Activities of the Southern Kaduna People

Table 4.10: Effects of Banditry and Kidnappings

Effects of banditry and kidnappings	Frequency	Percent
Destruction of lives and properties	380	99.5
Disruption of cropping activities	331	86.6
Rendering people as refuges	273	71.5
Disruption of economic activities	203	53.1
Psychological trauma suffered by residents, victims and relatives of victims of armed banditry	347	90.8
Disruption of social activities e.g. festivals, educational	367	96.1
Increase in poverty of local residents	370	96.9
Shortage in agricultural outputs of the farmers	369	96.6
Banditry has also caused fear and possible death	123	32.2

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 4.10 presents information on the effects of banditry and kidnappings in the area. The respondents were asked of how banditry and kidnappings has affected them, and their responses showed that; Destruction of lives and properties (99.5%), increase in poverty of local residents (96.9%), Shortage in agricultural outputs of the farmers (96.6%), Disruption of social activities e.g. festivals, educational(96.1%), Psychological trauma suffered by residents, victims and relatives of victims of the banditry (90.8%), disruption of cropping activities (86.6%), rendering people as refuges (71.5%),disruption of economic activities (53.1%), banditry has also cased fear and possible death (32.2%).These among others are some of the effects that were impacted on the residents of southern Kaduna.

Ways of Avoiding Being Kidnapped

Table 4.11Ways of Avoiding Being Kidnapped

Effects of banditry and kidnappings	Frequency	Percent
Pray to avoid being a victim	378	99.0
Stop routine movement	347	90.8
Don't discuss your family matters with strangers	377	98.7
Do proper checks before employing peoples services	331	86.6
Maintain a moderate lifestyle	369	96.6
Don't discuss money publicly	379	99.2
Know your neighbours	376	93.4
Don't get too close to strangers	203	53.1
Keep emergency numbers	263	68.8
Be aware of your environment	347	90.8
Always keep your phone(s) handy	337	88.2
Attract the attention of people whenever you notice a threat	381	99.7
Let someone know where you are going	203	53.1
Do not accept rides from strangers	381	99.7
Be careful with revealing data on social media	367	96.1
Be vigilant not only at night but at all times	223	58.4
Keep your financial transaction very confidential	369	96.6
Avoid public donations	373	97.6
Don't be predictable	357	93.5

Source: Field survey, 2022

Table 4.11 presents the different ways to avoid being abducted or kidnapped. 99% of the respondents agreed that prayer, avoiding discussing money publicly, and alert people's attention whenever you notice a threat and refusing to accept rides from strangers are among the major solution to avoid being kidnapped or abducted.

Others such as avoiding public donations, avoiding discussing your family matters with strangers, maintaining a moderate lifestyle among others are some of the tips when observed will go a long way in preventing the rate of abduction and kidnapping in an area.

CONCLUSION

From the forego discussions, it is evidence that the activities of banditry and kidnapers in the study area to a greater extent have impacted negatively on the wellbeing of the affected residents and Nigeria at large. The study deduced that the menace of banditry is becoming worrisome as result of high level of unemployment, weak security system, poverty, porosity of Nigeria's borders, arms proliferations and the presence scarcely governed spaces which serve as hideouts to the bandits. Consequently, the work reveals that there have been high incidences of banditry attacks on farm settlements, villages, and highways resulting in kidnapping in the study area with attendant security challenges. The study thus concluded that Nigeria security has been quite tense and volatile in the due to the alarming rate of banditry with the attendant massive marauding and bloodshed, which has turn the region into a state of insecurity in all spheres of life.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In order to deal with the threat of banditry in the study area and Nigeria at large, the following recommendations are made:

1. Nigeria government should sustain the military efforts in prosecuting the war against banditry and equip the security forces with modern equipments and necessary incentives to enhance their performance.
2. There is need for massive employment of youths in the armed forces of Nigeria.
3. Nigerian government should create meaningful employment for the youths through programmes aim at addressing the endemic poverty in the country.
4. There should be re-orientation to inculcate ethical values and reverence for life and human right and the need to co-exist among the populace.
5. Government at all levels should put in place functional security system like community policing to supplement the operations of other security agencies.
6. There is the need for proper collaboration between the army, police and Vigilante Groups for effective policing of the Communities.
7. There should be adequate deployment of modern technology for security surveillance to check trans-border crimes, which promotes banditry in Nigeria.

REFERENCES

- Abdullahi, A. (2019). Rural banditry, regional security, and integration in West Africa. *Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, 2(3), 644-654.
- Achumba, I. C., Ighomereho, O. S. & Akpor-Rabaro, M. O. M. (2013). Security challenges in Nigeria and the implications for business activities and sustainable development. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 4(2), 2222-2855.
- Adegoke, S. G. (2019). Insurgency, armed banditry and corruption in Nigeria: The bane of socio-economic underdevelopment. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Studies*, 2(1), 17-26.
- Adeniyi, T. (2015). Why incoming FCT Minister must act fast on cattle rustling. *Daily Trust*, July 1st. Retrieved from: Chikun, Jaba, Jema'a, Kachia, Kaduna South, Kagarko, Kajuru, Kaura, Kauru, Lere, Sanga, ZangonKataf

- www.dailytrust.com.ng /daily/index.php/city-news/58662-why-incoming -fct- administrationmust-act-fast-on-cattle-rustling>
- Akowe, T. & Kayode, B. (2014). Cattle rustling: A northern nightmare. *The Nation*, March 30th. Retrieved from: <http://thenationonline.net/cattle-rustling-northern-nightmare>>
- Asmau, D. & Abdulrasheed, O. (2020). Effects of armed banditry on human security in Kaduna State. *FUDMA Journal of Politics and International Affairs (FUJOPIA)*, 3(2), 110-116.
- Bashir, M. (2014). Hopes for an end to cattle theft. *Daily Trust*, September 4th. Retrieved from: www.dailytrust.com.ng/daily/feature/33468-hopes-for-an-end-to-cattle-theft>
- Beland, D. (2005). The political construction of collective insecurity: From moral panic to blame avoidance and organized irresponsibility. *Center for European Studies, Working Paper Series* 126.
- Berkowitz, L. (1989). Frustration-aggression hypothesis: Examination and reformulation. *Psychological Bulletin*, 106(1), 59-73.
- Dollard J, Miller, N. E, Doob, L. W., Mowrer, O. H., & Sears, R. R. (1939). *Frustration and aggression*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
- Egwu, S. (2016). The political economy of rural banditry in contemporary Nigeria. In Kuna, M.J and Ibrahim, J (eds.). *Rural banditry and conflicts in northern Nigeria*, Abuja: Centre for Democracy and Development.
- Fererabend, I. K. & Feiraubend, R. L. (1972). Systematic conditions of political aggression: An application of frustration-aggression theory. In Fairaben and Ted, R.C. (eds) *Anger violence and politics: Theories and research*. Prentice Hall Inc, Englewood. Cliff, New Jersey.
- Igbuzor, O. (2011). Peace and security education: A critical factor for sustainable peace and national development. *International Journal of Peace and Development Studies*, 2(1), 1-7.
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970): Determining Sample Size for Research Activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 30, 607-610.
- Kuna, M. J. & Jibrin.I. (eds.) (2016). *Rural banditry and conflicts in Northern Nigeria*, Abuja: Centre for Democracy and Development.
- Lyman, P. M. G. (2007). *Organised crime* (4th Ed). Prentice Hall: Person Education Inc.
- Mallory, S. (2007). *Theories on the continued existence of organised crime*. Sad bury Massachusetts: Jones and Barlet publishers.
- Maureen, O. M. & Blessing, N. O. (2018). Insurgency and its implication on Nigeria economic growth. *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, 7(2), 492-501.
- Miller, N. E. (1941). The frustration-aggression hypothesis. *Psychological Review*, 48, 337-342.
- Mustapha, U. N. (2019). Armed banditry and internal security in Zamfara State. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 10(8), 1219-1226.
- Nwanegbo, C. J., & Odigbo, J. (2013). *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 2(4), 285-291.
- Nwoye, K.O. (2000). Corruption, leadership and dialectics of development in Africa: An explanatory perspective. Enugu: Associated printers and Litho.
- Oche, O. (2001). Democratization and the management of African security. *Nigerian Journal of International Affairs*, 12(1).
- Ogunleye, G. O., Adewale, O. S., Alese, B. K. & Ogunde, A. O. (2013). A computer-based-security framework for crime prevention in Nigeria. A paper Presented at the 10th International Conference of the Nigeria Computer Society held from July 25th-29th Lagos.
- Okoli, A. C. & Ochim, F. (2016). Forestlands and national security in Nigeria: A threat-import analysis. *IIARD International Journal of Political and Administrative Studies*, 2(2), 43-53.
- Okoli, A. C. & Ogayi, C. O. (2018). Herdsmen militancy and humanitarian crisis in Nigeria: A theoretical briefing. *African Security Review*, 27(2), 129-143.
- Okoli, A. C. & Orinya, S. (2013). Oil pipeline vandalism and Nigeria's national security. *Global Journal*

of Human Social Sciences, XIII(v), 67-75.

- Olabanji, O. E. & Ese, U. (2014). Insecurity and socio-economic development in Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development Studies*, 5(1), 40-63.
- Olaniyan, A. & Yahaya, A. (2016). Cows, bandits, and violent conflicts: Understanding cattle rustling in northern Nigeria. *Africa Spectrum*, 51(3), 93-105.
- Olaniyan, A. (2018). Foliage and violence: Interrogating forests as a security threat in Nigeria. *African Security Review*, 27(1), 1-20.
- oligarchyby- prof-abubakar-liman/>
- Omede, A. J. (2011). Nigeria: Analysing the security challenges of the Goodluck Jonathan administration. *Canadian Social Science*, 7(5), 90-102.
- Shalangwa, M. W. (2013). *The nature and consequences of armed banditry in border communities of Adamawa State, Nigeria*. M.Sc. thesis submitted to the School of Post-Graduate Studies, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria.
- Suleiman, A. O. (2017). Thematic Appraisal on the impulsive upsurge of yahoo-yahoo in the 21st Century in Nigeria: Qur'anic standpoint.
- Tauna, A. (2016). We have tamed cattle rustling, we will tame kidnapping-Northern governors. *Daily Post*, January 30th. Retrieved from: <http://dailypost.ng/2016/01/30/we-have-tamed-cattle-rustling- wewill-tackle-kidnapping-northern-governors>
- Uche, J. C. & Iwuamadi, C. K. (2018). Nigeria: Rural banditry and community resilience in the Nimbo community. *Conflict Studies Quarterly*, (24), 71-82.
- Yusuf, V. (2015). Deadly persistence of cattle rustling. *Daily Trust*, May 16th. Retrieved from: www.dailytrust.com.ng/weekly/index.php/features/20488-deadly-persistence-of-cattle-rustling.